

NOTES

A note on the Possibility of Transforming an Equation derived for Electro-osmosis with Surface Conductance correction into the corresponding Electrophoretic Equation

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It has been shown that the following equation derived for electro-osmosis.

$$\zeta = \zeta_a \left[1 + \frac{3 V_1 \beta x}{V R k} \right] \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

assumes the form

$$\zeta = \zeta_a \left(1 + \frac{x}{kR} \right) \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

under the conditions of electrophoresis for values of $kR > 100$. Where ζ and ζ_a are the true and apparent electrokinetic potential, V , the total volume of the n -solid non-conducting particles, each of radius R , β is a factor by which $\frac{3V_1}{R}$ is to be multiplied to get the effective surface area, x the specific surface conductance of the particles, V , the volume of the solution within the diaphragm and k the bulk specific conductivity of the solution.

For values of $kR > 100$ Henry's equation for electrophoresis of non-conducting spherical particles also assume the same form as equation (4).

It has been shown in two previous papers^{1,2} that the true ζ -potential can be evaluated from electro-osmotic data according to the following equation; where ζ_a is the apparent

$$\zeta = \zeta_a \left[1 + \frac{3 V_1 \beta x}{R V k} \right] \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

potential calculated from electro-osmotic data using Smoluchowski equation, V_1 , the total volume of the solid consisting of n particles each of radius R contained in the diaphragm,

β a factor with which $\frac{3 V_1}{R}$ is to be multiplied to obtain the effective surface area, V ,

the volume of the solution in the diaphragm, k the specific conductivity of the solution in bulk and x the specific surface conductance.

In the equation (1), $\frac{3 V_1}{R} = 4 n \pi R^2$ - the total surface area of the n particles

1. B. N. Ghosh, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1955, Heft. 5, S. 121.

2. B. N. Ghosh and P. K. Pal, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1961, 57, 118.

contained in the diaphragm. For each of the three directions in space the effective surface area would be $1/3 (4 \pi R^2)$. Therefore, the effective surface area parallel to the direction of the electric current should be $1/3 (\pi 4\pi R^2)$ or $\beta=1/3$. Introducing these values of V_f/R and β in equation (1) and putting $V/n = V_f$ it may be written as

$$\zeta = \zeta_a \left[1 + \frac{4}{3} \frac{\pi R^2}{V_f} \frac{x}{k} \right] \quad (2)$$

In equation (2) V_f represents the volume of solution per particle.

To satisfy the minimum requirement of electrophoresis V_f should be increased so that the particles forming the diaphragm are separated from one another. It should be noted that when a particle of radius R moves in an applied electric field, the cross-sectional area of the solution over which the field is distorted must be of the same order as that of the particle and its ion atmosphere taken together i.e., $\pi (R + \frac{1}{k})^2$ where $\frac{1}{k}$ is the thickness of the ion atmosphere. Outside this cross-sectional area the electric current will not be affected by the presence of the particle. Again V_f should represent such a volume of solution as would fill the space which remains vacant in a cube each side of which is $(2R + \frac{4}{k})$ and whose centre is occupied by the particle. Calculation on the basis of these considerations indicates that V_f should be put equal to the volume of a sphere of radius $(R + 1/k)$. Further increase in V_f would have little influence on electrophoresis. Making this substitution in equation (2) and simplifying, the following equation is obtained

$$\zeta = \zeta_a = \left[1 + \frac{x}{k} \frac{1}{R(1+1/kR)} \right] \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

when $kR > 100$, $1/kR$ may be neglected compared to unity and so equation (3) assumes the form

$$\zeta = \zeta_a \left[1 + \frac{x}{kR} \right] \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

It has been shown by Ghosh, Ray and Raychowdhury³ that for large values of (kR) , Henry's⁴ equation for electrophoresis becomes identical with equation (4).

Thus equation (1) derived for electro-osmosis assumes under the conditions of electrophoresis, when $kR > 100$, the form of equation (4) which is identical with Henry's equation for electrophoresis of non-conducting spherical particles.

3. B. N. Ghosh, K. C. Ray and P. B. Roychowdhury, *J. Ind. Chem. Sec.*, 1955, **32**, 29.

4. D. C. Henry, *Trans. Farad. Sec.*, 1948, **44**, 1021.